

PACIFICUS

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“A BALLAD FOR MY BESTIE”

You left me with a fainting smile,
the ghost of laughter on your lips,
and walked into that endless aisle
where time dissolves and sunlight slips.

I took the reins with trembling hands,
the children clustering near my knees,
and tried to follow your commands
through lonely nights and anxious seas.

The years rolled on like slow, gray waves;
I watched them grow, I watched them soar,
the little ones you never saved
a seat for, waiting at the door.

They blossomed, each one, strong and bright,
with your brave heart, your gentle way,
and in their faces, clear as light,
I saw you living, day by day.

I thank the God who took you hence,
though selfish tears still find my eyes,
for in your leaving, the evidence
of love that never truly dies.

Your body lost, but not your soul,
it walks beside me, speaks inside,

a steady hand, a constant goal,
a refuge where I run to hide.

And yet, dear heart, I must confess,
in quiet hours when evening falls,
I cannot help but wish you less
a spirit and more these four walls.

To see you slouched in your old chair,
to hear your laugh, to touch your hand,
not just your presence in the air,
but solid, warm, as love demands.

So here's my ballad, simple, true,
for you, my bestie, gone from sight.
You may not be around, but you
are still my dearest, still my light.

The children flourish, strong and free,
and I endure, and sometimes smile,
all because you left to me
that fainting smile to walk each mile.

For those from SUCs who wish to use this for promotion, the guidelines are stated in the last part.

"Please submit each title as a separate file and rename each file using the title of your work followed by the category of the literary piece.

Example: NAME OF TITLE_POETRY"

Categories

Please **HIGHLIGHT** the category that best fits your submission:

- ◇ **Poetry**
- ◇ **Short Stories**
- ◇ **Essays**
- ◇ **Spotlight on Emerging Writers**
- ◇ **Creative Corner**
- ◇ **Others:** _____ (Please specify)

After you fill this out, kindly send it to our official email at **binasbookers2013@gmail.com**. Make sure that your work is final before you send it, as any revisions will no longer be accommodated once the process starts. The entire publication will be posted on our official site once it is finalized, at this link:

<https://sites.google.com/view/binasbookers2013/home>

The online publication process typically takes **7 to 10 days**. However, if you opt for a publication that includes **peer review**, the timeline may vary depending on the availability of reviewers. We appreciate your patience and understanding in this matter.

If you want a hand-signed certificate, we can provide you with a copy. However, you will be responsible for the shipping fee: **₱450 for Luzon, ₱300 for Visayas, and ₱450 for Mindanao.**

"This literary magazine will be published both online and in print. The online version is free. After the publication is finalized, we will provide you with the full copy in PDF format. If you wish to print it, you may do so on your own."

FOR SUCs: These are the Guidelines for JC Reclassification

Section 25. Creative Works Produced, Performed, Presented, Exhibited, or Published

1. Creative works encompass a wide range of artistic and intellectual expressions, including, but not limited to, music, dance, drama, theatrical productions, visual arts, architecture, industrial design, and literary publications.
2. Creative works should align with the faculty member's field of specialization. However, creative works outside the faculty member's specialization may be considered, provided that the creative work is supported by and has brought recognition to the SUC, as evidenced by the following:
 - a. The faculty member's involvement in creative activities was authorized by the SUC (e.g., special order, memorandum, or official communication);
 - b. There is documented evidence that the development of the creative work was supported by the SUC (e.g., approved project proposal, partnership agreements, or authorization for the use of facilities for the creative work);
 - c. The creative work has brought recognition to the institution, as demonstrated by awards or other formal acknowledgments received by the SUC, with the SUC's name explicitly cited in the announcement or the university formally recognized as the institution behind the award or recognition.

According to the guideline, ***“Creative works should align with the faculty member's field of specialization,”*** please ensure that your submission aligns with your field. Otherwise, we will rely on the provision in item **c**, which states that the ***“SUC's name [must be] explicitly cited in the announcement or the university formally recognized as the institution behind the award or recognition.”***

Under your name on the certificate, we will indicate your school's name.

